

Why is the net magnetic flux through a closed surface zero?

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According to Gauss's Law for Magnetism, the total magnetic flux through any closed surface is always zero.

As previously stated in my earlier paper, I propose that the proton and electron are not simply charges with different electrical properties.

Instead, I think they are the same type of charge that exhibits opposite rotational directions—according to Fleming's rules—when occupying the same space or moving in the same direction.

Figure 1. Electric Flux Tube

Figure 1 illustrates an electric flux tube, representing the model of $\Phi = EA\cos\theta$.

Inside the electric flux tube, an electric field E is present; the surface area of the cylindrical exterior is A , which is curved as shown in $\cos\theta$.

Charges move from left to right, as indicated by the arrows in the figure. In this case, protons rotate clockwise while electron rotate counter-clockwise.

This results in the presence of two up-protons and one down-electron, whose clockwise rotational force is reduced by half.

$$F = \frac{1}{2}(E + B) + (E - B) + \frac{1}{2}(E + B);$$

$$q_1^+ = \frac{1}{2}, q^- = 1, q_2^+ = \frac{1}{2};$$

$$F = 2E. \quad (1)$$

Electrons and protons have intrinsic rotation (spin).

I removed velocity from the electromagnetic force formula and considered only the magnetic field.

This can be formulated as shown in equation (1).

Consequently, the total magnetic flux—that is, the sum of the magnetic fields—within the electric flux becomes zero, resulting in a neutron.

From the perspective of a single neutron, the two protons and one electron appear as particles because their waves are smaller than the neutron's envelope, whereas the neutron itself exhibits wave-like characteristics.

From a broader view, if this flux tube-shaped wave extends symmetrically on both sides, it will vibrate rather than rotate; however, if it extends asymmetrically, it will rotate.

As this envelope elongates, it takes on the structure of a wave packet,

which manifests as the shapes of objects we observe in everyday life.